

Os^{II}-carbonyl complexes of bidentate thioarylazoimidazoles and their catalytic efficiency to alcohol oxidation

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[OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR^l)]⁺ (**2**) (SRaaiNR^l (**1**) = 1-alkyl-2-*o*-thioalkylphenylazoimidazole) act as catalyst to the oxidation of primary/secondary alcohols to aldehyde/ketone by N-methylmorpholine N-oxide (NMO). The catalysts have been characterized by the spectroscopic data and two of the complexes [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNMe)]PF₆ (**2a**) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNEt)]PF₆ (**2b**) have been structurally characterized by single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements. The complexes are redox active and show Os^{III}/Os^{II} (~0.8 V) and Os^{IV}/Os^{III} (~1.5 V) couples. The catalytic activity of the complexes may be due to oxidation to Os^{IV}=O species by NMO (supported by $\nu(\text{Os}=\text{O})$, 857 cm⁻¹) which could oxidize alcohols to aldehydes or ketones.

Keywords: Os-H-carbonyl, thioarylazoimidazole, X-ray structure, redox, DFT and catalysis.

Introduction

On considering environment and growing economic concern the development of catalytic processes for alcohol oxidation is becoming increasingly important¹. Ruthenium and osmium complexes act as efficient catalysts in the synthesis of organic-oxo compounds such as oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols to aldehydes and ketones². In this aspect Ru^{II} complexes³⁻⁶ of arylazo ligands appear more frequent than Os^{II} complexes^{7,8}. The π -acidity of azoimine functionalised ligand has important role for stabilization of the coordination complexes of the metal ions in particular to lower oxidation state⁹. The M-CO chemistry of arylazo-heterocycles are relatively underdeveloped and has been started very recently⁴⁻⁷. We have designed different arylazoimidazoles with reference to the variation of electron donating and withdrawing substituents and also on addition of extra donor centres at suitable position to phenyl backbone to increase denticity of the ligand. In this work we use 1-alkyl-2-*o*-thioalkylphenylazoimidazole (SRaaiNR^l (**1**)) as ligand who could chelate either bidentate¹⁰ N,N'- or tridentate N,N',S-chelator¹¹ to synthesize Os-CO complexes. The complexes are spectroscopically characterized and some of the complexes are structurally confirmed by single crystal X-

ray diffraction studies and it is shown that the ligand, SRaaiNR^l, serves as bidentate N,N' chelating agent. The oxidation of primary/secondary alcohols by NMO (N-methylmorpholine N-oxide) has been catalysed by these Os^{II}-complexes into their respective aldehydes/ketones. DFT computation has been attempted to explain spectral and redox properties of the complexes.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation of the complexes

Osmium complexes, [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR^l)]PF₆ (**2**) are synthesized by the reaction of [OsHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃] and 1-alkyl-2-*o*-thioalkylphenylazoimidazoles (SMeaaiNMe (**1a**), SMeaaiNEt (**1b**), SEtaaiNEt (**1c**) and SEtaaiNMe (**1d**)) (1:1 mole ratio) under refluxing condition in acetonitrile (Scheme 1) followed by the addition of NH₄PF₆ and chromatographic purification. The molar conductance measurements of the complexes, **2** support 1:1 electrolyte nature (90–100 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in acetonitrile. The microanalytical data support the composition of the complexes.

The complexes, **2**, show sharp stretch at 1929–1936 cm⁻¹ those correspond to $\nu(\text{CO})$. A weak stretch at 2090–2098 cm⁻¹ is assigned to $\nu(\text{Os-H})$ ⁷. The $\nu(\text{CO})$ is the indica-

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R = R' = Me (**1a**, **2a**); R' = Et, R = Me (**1b**, **2b**); R = R' = Et (**1c**, **2c**);
R' = Me, R = Et (**1d**, **2d**); anion is PF₆⁻ (**2**)

Scheme 1. The ligand, SRaaiNR' (**1**) and the complexes, [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR')]PF₆ (**2**).

tor of extend of participation of metal d π -orbital in the π -back bonding process and follows: $\nu(\text{CO})$ (free ligand) > $\nu(\text{CO})$ (complex **2**). The σ -effect of H⁻ in **2** may be the reason for efficient back-bonding interaction with Os-CO^{4,7}. Infrared spectra of the complexes exhibit $\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ at 1378–1390 and 1554–1583 cm⁻¹ respectively (see Experimental Section). The azo (-N=N-) stretching is significantly shifted to lower frequency compared to free ligand value (1400–1410 cm⁻¹)⁹ which supports d $\pi(\text{Os}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{N}=\text{N})$ back donation in the complexes. The $\nu(\text{PF}_6)$ appears at 765–775 and 820–828 cm⁻¹ in the complexes.

Natural bond orbital analysis of [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNMe)]⁺ (**2a**⁺) has been carried out on the DFT optimized geometry to understand the Os-CO bonding in the complexes. The C-O and Os-C have three and one natural bond orbitals respectively. The functional occupancies and hybridization of CO and Os-C bonds, energies are summarized in Tables S1, S2. The anti-bonding population of NBOs lies in 0.23–0.24 a.u. which indicates the higher extent of back-donation d $\pi(\text{Os}^{\text{II}}) \rightarrow \pi^*$ orbitals of CO in the complex¹². Increase in d $\pi(\text{Os}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{CO})$ charge donation decreases the C-O bond strength which means lowering of $\nu(\text{CO})$ as evident in lower $\nu(\text{CO})$, 1936 cm⁻¹ in **2a** than free CO. The NBO charge of Os atom is -1.058 which is much lower than +2 formal charge. The charge on carbonyl carbon is positive +0.697 in **2a** while oxygen atom is negative, -0.476 and the charges of other significant atomic centres are S(1), +0.351; P(1), +1.328; P(2), +1.341; N(1), -0.443; N(2), -0.356; N(3), -0.249; N(4), -0.116 a.u.

The absorption spectra are measured at room temperature in acetonitrile, and the bands are assigned on comparing reported results^{10,11} and have been determined by using the singlet-singlet vertical excitations calculated by TDDFT/CPCM model. The singlet state geometry of the complexes has been optimized in the ground state. Some of the calculated excitation wavelength and their assignment are given in (ESI[†], Table S3) for **2a**. Moderately intense bands at 485 and 396 nm of **2a** have been corroborated with HOMO-1 \rightarrow LUMO and HOMO-6 \rightarrow LUMO transitions and these are mixed metal-to-ligand and ligand-to-ligand charge transfer respectively. The band at 375 nm corresponds to intraligand charge transfer transition. Similarly, the weak broad band at 545 nm for **2a** corresponds to HOMO \rightarrow LUMO (mixed MLCT, ILCT) and at 570 nm (mixed MLCT, ILCT and XLCT) transitions in acetonitrile.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes show overlapping of many proton resonances due to their similar chemical shifts and individual assignment of proton signals is ambiguous; though the calculated numbers of equivalent aromatic protons (see Experimental Section) are observed in the spectra. The significant observation is triplet $\delta(\text{Os}-\text{H})$ at -10.26 ($J = 21.30$ Hz) (**2a**), -10.21 ppm ($J = 21.38$ Hz) (**2b**), -10.18 ppm ($J = 21.75$ Hz) (**2c**) and -10.28 ppm ($J = 21.45$ Hz) (**2d**). Triplet splitting pattern (ESI[†], Fig. S1) arises from coupling with two ³¹P nuclei⁷. The N-Me and S-Me appear as singlet at 3.89 and 1.92 ppm respectively in **2a**. The N-CH₂CH₃ and S-CH₂CH₃ show two quartet and two triplet signals in **2b-2d**. The ³¹P{¹H} NMR spectra exhibit one signal at negative δ -15.60 to -15.65 ppm of [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR')]PF₆ (**2**).

Molecular structures

The crystal structures of the complexes [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNMe)]PF₆ (**2a**) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNEt)]PF₆ (**2b**) are shown in Fig. 1 and bond parameters are given in Table 1. The molecules consist of cationic complex, [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR')]⁺ and PF₆⁻ as counter ion. The cation has a central Os atom surrounded by six donor centers, OsHCP₂N₂, and the arrangement is distorted octahedral. It is observed that SRaaiNR' behaves as a bidentate, N, N'-chelating ligand; other ligands are CO, two PPh₃, H. In **2a** and **2b** the SMeaaiNMe and SEtaaiNMe act as N, N'-chelating (imidazolyl-N (N), azo-N (N')) respectively; N, N', H⁻ and C(1) (CO) form a distorted square plane; two PPh₃ are *trans*

Fig. 1. Crystal structures of (i) **2a**⁺ and (ii) **2b**⁺.Table 1. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°) for **2a**⁺ and **2b**⁺

Bond distances (Å)	2a		2b X-Ray	Bond angles (°)	2a		2b X-Ray
	X-Ray	DFT			X-Ray	DFT	
Os(1)-C(1)	1.856(13)	1.870	1.865(13)	C(1)-Os(1)-N(4)	99.40(4)	99.84	105.70(5)
Os(1)-N(1)	2.099(9)	2.161	2.107(11)	N(1)-Os(1)-N(4)	75.00(3)	73.11	74.90(4)
Os(1)-N(4)	2.149(10)	2.204	2.157(10)	C(1)-Os(1)-P(1)	88.30(3)	91.09	89.40(4)
Os(1)-P(1)	2.368(3)	2.426	2.374(3)	N(1)-Os(1)-P(1)	92.60(2)	89.60	91.00(3)
Os(1)-P(2)	2.379(3)	2.452	2.369(3)	N(4)-Os(1)-P(1)	99.40(3)	100.60	99.60(3)
Os(1)-H(1)	1.580(6)	1.641	1.607(7)	C(1)-Os(1)-P(2)	90.50(3)	91.37	89.30(4)
C(1)-O(1)	1.179(14)	1.166	1.141(16)	N(1)-Os(1)-P(2)	90.10(2)	90.05	90.10(3)
N(3)-N(4)	1.288(13)	1.294	1.301(15)	N(4)-Os(1)-P(2)	96.10(3)	95.98	93.20(3)

oriented in the coordination sphere⁷. The chelate angles are $\angle N(4)-Os(1)-N(1)$, 88.30 (3)^o (**2a**) and 89.40 (4)^o (**2b**) and the angles of the *trans* configuration are ($\angle P(1)-Os-P(2)$, 164.4(11)^o (**2a**) and 166.94(11)^o (**2b**)).

The Os-N(azo) [Os(1)-N(4), N(4) is azo-N], 2.149(10) Å in **2a**, 2.143(7) Å in **2b**] is longer than Os-N(imidazolyl) [Os(1)-N(1), N(1) is imidazolyl-N, 2.099(9) Å in **2a**, 2.088(8) Å in **2b**]. In general the Os-N(azo) bond distance is shorter than Os-N(imidazolyl) bond length due to $d\pi(Os) \rightarrow \pi^*(N=N)$ back donation¹³. The -N=N- bond length, 1.288(13) Å (**2a**) and 1.291(11) Å (**2b**), is longer than free ligand azo distance, 1.267(3) Å¹⁴. The elongation of azo bond in complexes is

due to the extensive $d\pi(Os) \rightarrow \pi^*(N=N)$ back donation.

The structural parameters obtained from single crystal X-ray diffraction have been compared with DFT computed structure for **2a**. The calculation of the representative complexes are carried out using singlet state optimized geometry of cationic complex unit. The bond lengths are deviated in theoretically computed structures from experimental data by 0.002–0.1 Å and bond angles are shifted by 0.4–5°.

Electrochemistry

The complex **2** shows one quasireversible and one irreversible oxidative response positive to reference Ag/AgCl

electrode at 0.79–0.92 V ($\Delta E = 120$ – 130 mV) and 1.51–1.62 V respectively. One reversible reduction at -0.59 – 0.70 V ($\Delta E = 100$ – 110 mV) along with a quasireversible reduction peak has been observed at -1.10 – 1.21 V ($\Delta E = 120$ – 130 mV) is observed (Table 2). The DFT computed molecular functions have been used to explain redox information of the complexes. The HOMO of **2a**⁺ has 39% osmium *d*-orbital nature. Consequently, the oxidations are Os^{II}→Os^{III}, Os^{III}→Os^{IV} couples in **2**. Similarly, LUMOs of the complexes exclusively have ligand character and the reductions are referring to $[-N=N-/-N=N-]$ and $[-N=N-]/[-N=N-]$ ²⁻.

Table 2. Cyclic voltammetric data of **2** *n*-acetonitrile

Complex	Cyclic voltammetric data ^a		
	E_{pa} (Os ^{IV} /Os ^{III}), V	$E_{1/2}^b$, V (ΔE_p , mV) (Os ^{III} /Os ^{II})	Ligand reductions, $E_{1/2}^b$, V (ΔE_p , mV)
2a	1.507	0.803(90)	-0.663(90) -1.102(130)
2b	1.621	0.920(95)	-0.598(85) -1.213(125)
2c	1.568	0.820(90)	-0.701(95) -1.164(120)
2d	1.609	0.798(90)	-0.620(90) -1.184(130)

^aIn acetonitrile solution, supporting electrolyte Bu₄NClO₄ (0.1 M), reference electrode SCE.

^b $E_{1/2}^b = 0.5(E_{pa} + E_{pc})$ where E_{pa} and E_{pc} are anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively; $\Delta E_p = E_{pa} - E_{pc}$; scan rate = 50 mV s⁻¹.

Catalytic oxidation of alcohols

The catalytic transformation of primary and secondary alcohols into their corresponding aldehydes and ketones is an essential reaction in organic synthesis. Osmium complexes have been extensively investigated as catalysts for alcohol oxidation in combination with oxidant NMO. The substrate, primary and secondary alcohols (1 mmol), were efficiently oxidized by using 0.1 mmol of the catalyst in the co-existence of 3 mmol of NMO in dichloromethane (Scheme 2). All the complexes oxidize primary alcohols to corresponding aldehydes and secondary alcohols to corresponding ketones. This reaction provides an eco-friendly route to the conversion of alcoholic functions to carbonyl groups. By-product H₂O of the reaction was removed by using molecular sieves (0.5 g). The aldehydes and ketones formed after 4 h of reflux were isolated qualitatively by the formation of 2,4-

Scheme 2. Oxidation of alcohol to aldehyde/ketone by NMO in presence of [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SEtaaiNMe)](PF₆) (**2d**) as catalyst.

dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives and characterized by FT-IR, UV-Vis spectral analysis. Control experiments were carried out without [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaaiNR')](PF₆) under the same reaction conditions and in no case was there any detectable oxidation of alcohols. A plot of percentage conversion of cyclohexanol as a function of time (min) with complex (**2a**) and (**2d**) in presence of NMO is noted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Profile of the percentage conversion of cyclohexanol as a function of time (min) with complex [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaaiNMe)]PF₆ (**2a**) (◇) and [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SEtaaiNMe)]ClO₄ (**2d**) (■) in presence of NMO.

The complexes catalyse the oxidation of PhCH₂OH to PhCHO (GC yield (%): 21.6 (**2a**), 21.9 (**2b**), 23.0 (**2c**), 22.7 (**2d**), C₄H₉OH (2-butanol) to C₄H₇O (2-butanone) (yield (%): 34.0 (**2a**), 33.6 (**2b**), 32.3 (**2c**), 33.0 (**2d**)), PhCH(OH)Ph (benzylalcohol) to PhCOPh (benzophenone) (yield (%): 37.8 (**2a**), 37.1 (**2b**), 37.0 (**2c**), 37.1 (**2d**)), and CyCH-OH (cyclohexanol) to CyC=O (cyclohexanone) (yield (%): 38.4 (**2a**), 37.0 (**2b**), 37.0 (**2c**), 42.3 (**2d**)). The catalytic oxidation yield is found to be highest in cyclohexanol. The appearance of a peak at 858 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum is attributed to the formation of high-valent Os^{IV}=O species⁷ (ESI[†], Fig. S3), which is absent in the osmium catalyst. A plausible mecha-

nism of involvement of catalyst in the oxidation process is shown in Scheme 3. On comparing the catalytic activity of Ru^{II} complexes of arylazoimidazoles present series of complexes are relatively weak⁴ and show lower conversion rate which supports sluggish reaction of osmium complexes under identical reaction condition. Involvement of the ground state function of the catalyst, [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNMe)]⁺, in the oxidation process is very important. The occupied molecular functions (HOMO *etc.*) have 22–36% osmium feature which may be assisting Os^{II} to Os^{IV}=O formation (ESI[†], Table S1; Fig. S2). PPh₃ contribution (17%) is less than Os contribution (22%) which implies sacrificial oxidation of metal centre.

Scheme 3. Plausible pathway of catalytic oxidation of cyclohexanol with [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaiNR')PF₆] in presence of NMO.

Experimental

Materials and instrumentation

[OsHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃] was prepared by reported method¹⁵. The synthesis of the ligands (SRaaiNR') was carried out following the common procedure¹⁶. 2-Aminothiophenol was purchased from Aldrich. Other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade and used as received. For spectroscopic studies HPLC grade solvents were used.

Microanalytical data (C, H, N) were collected on Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. Infrared spectra were taken on a RX-1 Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer with

samples prepared as KBr pellets. UV-Vis spectral studies were performed on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 25 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker (AC) 300 MHz FTNMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ relative to tetramethylsilane and ³¹P (202 MHz) were obtained relative to 85% H₃PO₄ at room temperature. The absolute values of the coupling constants are given in Hertz (Hz). Multiplicities are abbreviated as singlet (s), doublet (d), triplet (t), multiplet (m), and broad (br).

Cyclic voltammetric measurements within ±2 V were carried out using a CHI Electrochemical workstation. A platinum wire working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode were used in a standard three-electrode configuration. [nBu₄N][ClO₄] was used as the supporting electrolyte in acetonitrile and the scan rate used was 50 mV s⁻¹ in acetonitrile under dinitrogen atmosphere. The reported potentials are uncorrected for junction potential and catalytic oxidation study was carried using Agilent 7890 series GC instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) using a HP-5 column of 30 m length, 0.53 mm diameter and 5.00 μm film thickness.

Synthesis of the complexes

[OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SMeaaiNMe)]PF₆ (**2a**):

To an 20 mL acetonitrile suspension of [OsHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃] (0.100 g, 0.10 mmol) 15 mL acetonitrile solution of SMeaaiNMe (**1a**) (0.026 g, 0.11 mmol) was added in (1:1) molar ratio and the solution was refluxed for 4 h under N₂ atmosphere. The colour of the solution changed from orange-red to dark red. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure using rota-evaporator. Red gummy mass so left was dissolved in minimum volume of methanol and aqueous solution of NH₄PF₆ was added to precipitate the products. The precipitate was filtered and washed with cold water, finally dried in vacuo over P₄O₁₀. The dry mass was then dissolved in minimum volume of CH₂Cl₂ and subjected to chromatography separation on a silica gel column (60–120 mesh). The reddish colored complex **2a** was eluted by 1:5 toluene-acetonitrile. Evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure afforded pure complex **2a**. The yield was 73.19 mg (68%). The compound [OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SEtaaiNEt)]PF₆ (**2c**) was also synthesized following the same procedure using OsHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃ (100 mg, 0.10 mmol) and SEtaaiNEt (**1c**) (0.029 mg, 0.11 mmol). The yield was 79.44 mg (72%). The compounds **2b** and **2d** are also prepared using the simi-

lar procedure and the yield is ~71%.

Microanalytical data: Calcd. (Found). For $C_{48}H_{43}N_4OF_6P_3SOs$ (**2a**): C, 51.43 (51.05); H, 3.87 (3.51); N, 5.01 (4.95); IR data (KBr disc) (cm^{-1}): 2093 (ν_{Os-H}), 1936 (ν_{CO}), 1581 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1382 ($\nu_{N=N}$), 841 ($\nu_{PF_6^-}$); 1H NMR data in $CDCl_3$ (ppm): 6.83–7.89 (aromatic H's), 3.89 (N- CH_3 , s), 1.92 (S- CH_3 , s), -10.26 (Os-H, t, $J = 21.30$ Hz); ^{31}P NMR (202 MHz) in $CDCl_3$, -15.60 ppm; UV-Vis (CH_3CN): λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$): 545 (1493), 485 (2312), 375 (2763). For $C_{49}H_{45}N_4OF_6P_3SOs$ (**2b**): C, 51.85 (51.72); H, 4.01 (4.00); N, 4.94 (4.72); IR data (KBr disc) (cm^{-1}): 2092 (ν_{Os-H}), 1929 (ν_{CO}), 1582 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1390 ($\nu_{N=N}$), 842 ($\nu_{PF_6^-}$); 1H NMR data in $CDCl_3$ (ppm): 6.94–7.89 (aromatic H's), 4.59 (N- CH_2CH_3 , q, $J = 7.42$ Hz), 1.38 (N- CH_2CH_3 , t, $J = 7.13$ Hz), 1.87 (S- CH_3 , s), -10.21 (Os-H, t, $J = 21.38$ Hz); ^{31}P NMR (202 MHz) in $CDCl_3$, -15.67 ppm; UV-Vis (CH_3CN): λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$): 539 (2303), 486 (3784), 367 (6035). For $C_{50}H_{47}N_4OF_6P_3SOs$ (**2c**): C, 52.26 (52.07); H, 4.12 (4.01); N, 4.88 (4.72); IR data (KBr disc) (cm^{-1}): 2098 (ν_{Os-H}), 1930 (ν_{CO}), 1580 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1387 ($\nu_{N=N}$), 840 ($\nu_{PF_6^-}$); 1H NMR data in $CDCl_3$ (ppm): 6.97–7.98 (aromatic H's), 4.63 (N- CH_2CH_3 , q, $J = 7.02$ Hz), 1.44 (N- CH_2CH_3 , t, $J = 6.90$ Hz), 2.41 (S- CH_2CH_3 , q, $J = 7.34$ Hz), 0.98 (S- CH_2CH_3 , t, $J = 6.89$ Hz), -10.18 (Os-H, t, $J = 21.75$ Hz); ^{31}P NMR (202 MHz) in $CDCl_3$, -15.64 ppm; UV-Vis (CH_3CN): λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$): 534 (2693), 483 (4362), 360 (6471). For $C_{49}H_{45}N_4OF_6P_3SOs$ (**2d**): C, 51.85 (51.82); H, 4.01 (4.09); N, 4.94 (4.74); IR data (KBr disc) (cm^{-1}): 2096 (ν_{Os-H}), 1935 (ν_{CO}), 1583 ($\nu_{C=N}$), 1390 ($\nu_{N=N}$), 843 ($\nu_{PF_6^-}$); 1H NMR data in $CDCl_3$ (ppm): 6.95–7.68 (aromatic H's), 3.88 (N- CH_3 , s), 2.33 (S- CH_2CH_3 , q, $J = 7.45$ Hz), 0.99 (S- CH_2CH_3 , t, $J = 7.11$ Hz), -10.28 (Os-H, t, $J = 21.45$ Hz); ^{31}P NMR (202 MHz) in $CDCl_3$, -15.65 ppm; UV-Vis (CH_3CN): λ_{max} (ϵ , $M^{-1} cm^{-1}$): 539 (2784), 488 (3983), 361 (6519).

X-Ray crystal structure analysis

Details of crystal analyses (crystal size (mm)): $[OsH(CO)(PPh_3)_2(MeSaaiNMe)]PF_6$ (**2a**), 0.10x0.10x0.02 and $[OsH(CO)(PPh_3)_2(MeSaaiNEt)]PF_6$ (**2b**), 0.26x0.18x0.14; data collection and structure refinement data are given in Table 3. Crystal mounting was done on glass fibers with epoxy cement. Single crystal data collections were performed with an automated Bruker SMART APEX CCD diffractometer. Unit cell parameters were determined from least-squares refinement of setting angles with θ in the range $1.49 \leq \theta \leq$

Table 3. Crystallographic data of **2a** and **2b**

Complex	2a	2b
Formula	$C_{46}H_{47}F_6N_4O_3SP_3Os$	$C_{49}H_{45}F_6N_4OSP_3Os$
M_r	1157.07	1135.10
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Triclinic
Space group	P2(1)/n	P-1
a (Å)	17.151(4)	14.860(2)
b (Å)	15.044(3)	14.873(2)
c (Å)	19.556(4)	24.331(4)
α (°)	90.00	83.948(2)
β (°)	96.751(6)	88.523(2)
γ (°)	90.00	66.558(2)
Cell volume (Å ³)	5010.8(18)	4905.3(13)
Z	4	4
μ (mm ⁻¹)	2.748	2.803
T (K)	93(2)	293(2)
hkl range	-17 to 20, -16 to 18, -19 to 23	-18 to 18, -18 to 18, -29 to 29
ρ_{calcd} . (g cm ⁻³)	1.534	1.537
θ range (°)	1.49 to 25.34	1.50 to 26.04
Data/restraints/parameters	9105/0/607	18784/0/1168
R^a , $wR2^b$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0699, 0.1587	0.0590, 0.1624
$R1$, $wR2$ (all data)	0.0883, 0.1733	0.0818, 0.1805
GOF	1.105	1.088

^a $R = \sum |F_o - F_c| / \sum F_o$. ^b $wR = [\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2 / \sum wF_o^4]^{1/2}$ are general but w are different, $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.0556P)^2 + 2.1396P]$ for (**2a**) and $w = 1/[\sigma^2(F^2) + (0.1085P)^2 + 0.6247P]$ for (**2b**) where $P = (F_o^2 + 2F_c^2)/3$.

25.34° (**2a**) and $1.50 \leq \theta \leq 26.04^\circ$ (**2b**). Out of 31782 collected data 9105 for **2a** and 49918 collected data 18784 for **2b** with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ were used for structure solution. The hkl ranges are $-17 \leq h \leq 20$, $-16 \leq k \leq 18$, $-19 \leq l \leq 23$ for **2a** and $-18 \leq h \leq 18$, $-18 \leq k \leq 18$, $-29 \leq l \leq 29$ for **2b**. Reflection data were recorded using the ω scan technique. The structures were solved and refined by full-matrix least-squares techniques on F^2 using the SHELX-97 program^{17,18}. The absorption corrections were done by the multi-scan technique. All data were corrected for Lorentz and polarization effects, and the non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms were included in the refinement process as per the riding model. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms were constrained to ride on the respective carbon and Os atoms with isotropic displacement parameters equal to 1.2 times the equivalent isotropic displacement of their parent atom in all cases.

Catalytic activity

The catalytic activity of osmium(II) complexes (0.1 mmol) (2, 3) in oxidation of primary and secondary alcohols (1 mmol) were carried out in presence of N-methylmorpholine N-oxide (NMO) (3 mmol) as co-oxidant in CH₂Cl₂ (20 ml) in refluxing condition for 4 h and the solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was then extracted with diethyl ether (20 ml), concentrated to ≈1 ml and was analysed by Agilent 7890 series GC instrument equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID) using a HP-5 column of 30 m length, 0.53 mm diameter and 5.00 μm film thickness.

The complexes catalyse the oxidation of PhCH₂OH to PhCHO (GC yield (%): 21.6 (2a), 21.9 (2b), 23.0 (2c), 22.7 (2d)), C₄H₉OH (2-butanol) to C₄H₇O (2-butanone) (GC yield (%): 34.0 (2a), 33.6 (2b), 32.3 (2c), 33.0 (2d)), PhCH(OH)Ph (benzylalcohol) to PhCOPh (benzophenone) (GC yield (%): 37.8 (2a), 37.1 (2b), 37.0 (2c), 37.1 (2d)), and CyCH₂OH (cyclohexanol) to CyC=O (cyclohexanone) (GC yield (%): 38.4 (2a), 37.0 (2b), 37.0 (2c), 38.3 (2d)).

Computational methods

All computations were performed using the Gaussian03 (G03)¹⁹ software. The Becke's three-parameter hybrid exchange functional and the Lee-Yang-Parr nonlocal correlation functional^{19–21} (B3LYP) were used throughout. The 6-31G(d) basis set for C, H, N, O, S, P and Cl atoms. SDD basis set with effective core potential was employed for Os atom^{22–24}. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima and there are only positive eigen values. Natural bond orbital analyses were performed using the NBO 3.1 module. Vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries were computed for the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism in acetonitrile using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^{25–27}. Gauss Sum²⁸ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

Conclusion

[OsH(CO)(PPh₃)₂(SRaaⁱNR^j)](PF₆) (2) are characterized and have been explored their catalytic activity towards alcohol oxidation by NMO to their corresponding carbonyl compounds. A high valent Os^{IV}=O species is proposed as the active intermediate in the catalytic process as oxygen donor.

DFT calculation has been used to explain the spectra and redox properties of the complexes. This work has promoted in future to design azoimine-Os^{II} complexes and to define catalytic potential for finding highest efficiency to the oxidation of alcohols.

Supplementary materials

Crystallographic data for the structures 2a and 2b have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data center, CCDC No. 889526 and 785606, respectively. Copies of this information may be obtained free of charge from the Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK (E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or www: http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk).

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